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Screening for Lung Cancer with Low Dose Computed Tomography (LDCT)

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Abstract

Using samples of small cell lung tumors, a research team led by biologist Dr. Raymond discovered two new ways to induce tumor cell death. By activating ferroptosis, one of two subtypes of tumor cells can be targeted: first, iron-dependent cell death due to oxidative stress, and second, oxidative stress. Therefore, cell death can also be induced in a different way. Both types of cell death must be caused by drugs at the same time to eliminate the majority of the tumor mass.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues, Tumors; Prevention, Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

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Introduction

Despite many advances in treatment, the diagnosis of small cell lung cancer in particular means a poor prognosis. In Germany, a maximum of 8,000 new cases of small cell lung cancer (SCLC) are diagnosed each year. At the time of diagnosis, the cancer had found many holes to escape from the immune system. Cellular mechanisms, such as cell death regulated by apoptosis, are usually inactive at this stage. In this way, tumor cells can divide and spread almost without disturbance. High

cell division is characteristic of small cell lung cancer, which initially promises a good response to chemotherapy. Unfortunately, in many cases the success of chemotherapy is short-lived because the tumor cells resist treatment quickly; In addition, the tumor is made up of not just one but several cell types (so-called subgroups), each with unique strategies for escaping lethal therapy. Scientists are trying to find out which cell death pathways are still available. The activity of the gene was compared between cells taken from the patient inside and outside the tumor. Significant signaling pathways for traditional cell death

mechanisms were already shut down in the tumor before treatment in the early stages. In contrast, genes important for activating iron-dependent cell death by oxidative damage (ferptosis) were strongly activated in cancer cells. Simply put, they found that small lung cancer cells could be divided into two subgroups: neurons and endocrine cells, and non-neuronal cells. In the neuronal and endocrine subtypes, there are more active genes that would otherwise normally be found in hormone-producing neurons. Cells belonging to another subgroup do not have this property and therefore belong to the group of non-neural cells. Several experiments have shown that non-neuronal cells can be killed using the butyryl sulfoximine, which causes ferptosis [1-510].

Results and Discussion

In cells belonging to the subgroup of nerves, it was found that they protect themselves against oxidative stress by producing antioxidants, resulting in cell death. However, by adding the antioxidant inhibitor Auranofin, the researchers were able to kill these cells as well. Biologists have made important observations about the possible application of these findings in the treatment of small cell lung cancer; when targeting only one of two pathways, activating ferroptosis or preventing the production of antioxidants in a tumor consisting of cells in both subgroups, the cancer cells were able to escape lethal therapy. They did this by regulating their gene expression to reach a subgroup that could resist targeted individual therapy.

Conclusions

It is currently in clinical trials for cancer treatment. Auranofin, which inhibits the production of protective antioxidants in cancer cells, has been used to treat rheumatoid arthritis for decades. Future clinical trials using this combination therapy will determine the extent to which this targeted treatment option

improves the prognosis of small cell lung cancer patients.

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Authors' Brief Biographies

Prof. Dr. lireza Heidari, Ph.D., D.Sc. is a Full Distinguished Professor and Academic Tenure of Chemistry and also Enrico Fermi Distinguished Chair in Molecular Spectroscopy at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. He has got his Ph.D. and D.Sc. degrees from California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. Furthermore, he has double postdocs in Project Management, Oncology, Human Cancer Tissues and Synchrotron Radiation from Monash University, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia and also in Nano chemistry and Modern Molecular Electronic-Structure Computations Theory from California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. His research interests include Biophysical Chemistry, Biomolecular and Biomedical Spectroscopy, Quantum Chemistry, Nano chemistry, Modern Electronic Structure Computations, Theoretical Chemistry, Mathematical Chemistry, Computational Chemistry, Vibrational Spectroscopy, Molecular Modelling, Ab initio & Density Functional Methods, Molecular Structure, Biochemistry, Molecular Simulation, Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Medicinal Chemistry, Oncology, Synchrotron Radiation, Synchrocyclotron Radiation, LASER, Anti-Cancer Nano Drugs, Nano Drugs Delivery, ATR-FTIR Spectroscopy, Raman Spectroscopy, Intelligent Molecules, Molecular Dynamics, Biosensors, Biomarkers, Molecular Diagnostics, Numerical Chemistry, Nucleic Acids, DNA/RNA Monitoring, DNA/RNA Hypermethylation & Hypomethylation, Human Cancer Tissues, Human Cancer Cells, Tumors, Cancer Tissues, Cancer Cells, etc. He has participated at more than five hundred reputed international conferences, seminars, congresses, symposiums and forums around the world as yet. Also, he possesses many published articles in Science Citation Index (SCI)/International Scientific Indexing (ISI), Medline/PubMed and Scopus Journals. It should be noted that he has visited many universities or scientific and academic research institutes in different countries such as United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia,

New Zealand, Scotland, Ireland, Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Luxembourg, Romania, Greece, Russia, Estonia, Ukraine, Turkey, France, Swiss, Germany, Sweden, Norway, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, South Africa, Egypt, Brazil, Spain, Portugal, Mexico, Japan, Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Philippines, South Korea, China, India, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, etc. as research fellow, sabbatical and volunteer researcher or visitor and so on heretofore. He has a history of several years of teaching for college students and various disciplines and trends in different universities. Moreover, he has been a senior advisor in various industry and factories. He is expert in many computer programs and programming languages. Hitherto, he has authored more than twenty books and book chapters in different fields of Chemistry. Syne, he has been awarded more than one thousand reputed international awards, prizes, scholarships and honors. Heretofore, he has multiple editorial duties in many reputed international and peer-reviewed journals, books and publishers. Hitherward, he is a member of more than five hundred reputed international academic-scientific-research institutes around the world. It should be noted that he is currently the President of the American International Standards Institute (AISI), Irvine, California, USA and also Head of Cancer Research Institute (CRI) and Director of the Bio Spectroscopy Core Research Laboratory at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA.

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